

CHANGING LANDSCAPE OF FILIPINO EDUCATION: TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON TRADITIONAL VS. MODERNIZED APPROACHES TO TEACHING FILIPINO

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ABSTRACT

The education landscape in the Philippines has been undergoing significant transformations in recent years, driven by technological advancements and evolving pedagogical approaches. The research investigated the evolving educational landscape, focusing on Junior High School teachers' perceptions and appreciation of the Filipino subject amidst changes in Koronadal City during the 2023-2024 Academic Year. Utilizing a qualitative methodology, particularly the phenomenological approach, the study involved fifteen participants – Junior High School teachers from Koronadal National Comprehensive High School in DepEd Koronadal City Division, meeting specified inclusion criteria. Employing a purposive sampling technique, fifteen Filipino teachers from Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City participated. Data collection involved semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions, exploring teachers' perceptions and experiences regarding traditional and modernized teaching methods in Filipino education. Results indicated a predominant perception of traditional methods as teacher-centered, focusing on lectures and didactic instruction, leading to passive learning and limited engagement. Conversely, modernized approaches, integrating technology and collaborative tools, were viewed favorably for enhancing engagement and comprehension, particularly among audio-visual learners. Teachers' preferences for teaching methods were influenced by the learning environment, instructional materials, and personal styles. Technology use positively impacted engagement and appreciation but raised concerns about overreliance and hindering critical thinking skills. Recommendations were provided for the Department of

Education, curriculum developers, Filipino teachers, and future researchers. Suggestions included promoting professional development for digital literacy, designing curriculum frameworks that integrate modernized approaches, embracing a pedagogical mindset valuing both traditional and modern methods, and conducting longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of modernized teaching approaches.

Keywords: *Traditional, Modernized, Teachers' Perspectives, Filipino Education*

INTRODUCTION

The education landscape in the Philippines has been undergoing significant transformations in recent years, driven by technological advancements and evolving pedagogical approaches. One of the key subjects at the heart of this transformation is the Filipino subject, which plays a critical role in preserving the national language and culture. The traditional methods of teaching Filipino have been challenged by modernization, introducing new approaches and tools that potentially impact students' learning experiences and perspectives. (DepEd, 2013).

Historically, the teaching of the Filipino subject in the Philippines has been rooted in traditional pedagogical methods. It often emphasizes rote memorization, recitation, and grammatical rules. While these methods have their merits, they have also faced criticism for being less engaging and relevant to students in the modern era (Bernardo, 2017).

The advent of technology and modern teaching methodologies has brought new opportunities for teaching and learning Filipino. Digital resources, interactive multimedia, and online platforms have been integrated into language education to make it more engaging and interactive (Basco & Gonzales, 2019). These modernized approaches aim to bridge the gap between traditional classroom instruction and the digital age.

The Filipino subject is not only about language but also about culture and identity. With modernization, there is a concern that the preservation of the Filipino language and culture may be at risk. Ngag (2023) pointed out that Filipino students have limited knowledge in their own literature, which also affects how they appreciate Filipino as a language.

Modernized approaches often require teachers to adapt to new technologies and teaching strategies. It is essential to investigate whether teachers are adequately prepared and trained to deliver these modernized lessons effectively (DepEd, 2012). Insufficient teacher training can hinder the successful implementation of modernized approaches (Molina & Macasaquit, 2018).

This study aims to delve into this evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceive and appreciate the Filipino subject amidst these changes in Koronadal National

Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

This study aimed to delve into the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceive and appreciate the Filipino subject amidst these changes in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, this delved with the following questions:

1. How do Junior High School teachers perceive traditional teaching methods in Filipino education, and what are their attitudes toward these methods?
2. What are the modernized approaches to teaching Filipino that are currently being employed in high schools, and how do teachers view their effectiveness in comparison to traditional methods?
3. What are the key factors that influence Junior High School Teachers' preferences for either traditional or modernized approaches to learning the Filipino subject?
4. How does the use of technology and digital resources impact Junior High School Teachers' engagement with and appreciation of the Filipino subject?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research used a qualitative methodology, especially using the phenomenological approach, to delve into the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceived and appreciated the Filipino subject amidst these changes in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

One crucial element of the phenomenological research design is the researcher's responsibility to suspend any preexisting beliefs about the experience or phenomena in question (Delve & Limpaecher, 2012).

Participants of the Study

The participants' qualifications, as determined by the criteria established by the researcher before selecting eligible informants for the study. The study involved a total of fifteen (15) participants: comprised of Junior High School teachers from Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City, who met the researcher's specified inclusion criteria:

Participants' Inclusion Criteria:

Qualification: Teacher-Participants

1. Must be a Filipino teacher.
2. Must be assigned in Junior High School at Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City.
3. Must be in 5 years and above in teaching Filipino.

Sampling Technique

This study employed a Purposive Sampling Technique to carefully select fifteen (15) participants comprised of Junior High School Filipino teachers from Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City, who met the researcher's specified inclusion criteria.

This method of sampling patterned after Creswell (2013) mandates that researcher's possess prior knowledge of the objectives underpinning their study so as to effectively pinpoint and make contact with eligible participants through online survey platforms like Alchemer. Researcher's resort to purposive sampling in order to secure access to a distinct subgroup of individuals, whereby all survey respondents are meticulously chosen based on their alignment with a specific demographic or criterion.

Data Gathering Instrument

This research used a semi-structured interview as an investigative instrument during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). Its purpose was to explore the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceived and appreciated the Filipino subject amidst these changes in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

The validity and appropriateness of this tool were substantiated through a rigorous evaluation process conducted by a panel of experts who possess expertise in the development of relevant research instruments.

Data Gathering Procedure

To enhance the trustworthiness of the study, a rigorous adherence to a predetermined set of protocols was maintained. The main aim of this research was to delve into the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceived and appreciated the Filipino subject amidst these changes in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

During the preliminary stage, the researcher sought the approval from both the Superintendent of the Department of Education in Division of Koronadal City and the Dean of the College of Graduate Studies (CGS). The acquisition was crucial to get the

necessary permits for the researcher to carry out the study, hence underscoring the significance of ethical deliberations.

Subsequently, a supplementary letter of authorization was sent to the School Principal, expressly soliciting permission to get access to the precise data necessary for this study. A survey questionnaire was methodically constructed. It underwent rigorous examination and was given to the intended participants.

The researcher used a Purposive Sampling Technique to meticulously choose Junior High School teachers as participants for this investigation. Under the condition of strict compliance with specified health procedures, the researcher proceeded with the implementation of interviews and the facilitation of Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), all of which were carried out through in-person interactions.

The data obtained from interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs) underwent a systematic organization process, followed by a complete analysis and interpretation using the theme analysis technique. This methodology was anticipated to provide a more comprehensive comprehension of the matters being examined.

Data Analysis

The study aimed to examine the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceive and appreciate the Filipino subject amidst these changes in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

Following data collection, the transcripts were systematically reviewed to identify common themes and patterns emerging from the participants' responses which patterned after the study of Ngag (2023). Through an iterative process of coding and categorization, key themes were identified, reflecting the participants' perceptions, concerns, and insights regarding the agenda.

To achieve this objective, the researcher employed a content or thematic analysis approach to analyze the collected data. The approach described by Braun and Clarke (2006) that involves a systematic process of organizing textual components, such as sentences, phrases, and words, into organized groups or categories. The categorization of data will be based on either pre-existing frameworks or specifically designed categories that are tailored to the aims of the research.

To execute this analytical technique, a series of crucial stages was meticulously followed.

During the preliminary stage, several data sources, including interview transcripts, notes from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), and relevant documents, were

systematically organized and readied for analysis. This phase is crucial for ensuring the systematic arrangement and ease of access to the data.

Following this, the researcher was in an extensive examination of interview transcripts and focus group discussion (FGD) notes in order to thoroughly analyze the data. The immersive method facilitated the acquisition of a thorough comprehension of the content and context that was inherent in the acquired information.

The next phase involved commencing a systematic coding procedure. The generation of first codes included the identification of relevant segments or patterns within the data. The aforementioned codes served as a means of encapsulating essential concepts, ideas, or topics that was directly related to the roles of community and culture in shaping the academic motivation of Hiligaynon learners.

After the coding process, the detected codes were organized into preliminary themes based on their common meaning or significance. The objective of this stage was to develop a basic structure for organizing the data.

Following this, the prevalent patterns that have emerged and the associated categories assigned to them were subjected to a rigorous process of examination and improvement. The researchers maintained the consistency and clarity of these topics, making any essential revisions as required. A descriptive title was provided for each refined topic, which conveyed the material it covered. This aided in the simple identification and understanding of the themes.

The selection and linking of relevant data extracts, such as quotes or segments derived from interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs), were conducted concerning the corresponding topics. The provided passages functioned as corroborating evidence for the highlighted themes.

The researcher did a comprehensive analysis to understand the relevance and consequences of each topic within the specific context of the study's aims. The researcher analyzed trends, correlations, and variances within the identified topics to get a full understanding of the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceived and appreciated the Filipino subject.

The study employed a rigorous and systematic approach to thematic analysis, enabling researchers to comprehensively examine and comprehend the educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceived and appreciated the Filipino subject.

The said methodology provided significant findings that may help the improvement of intervention programs designed to address the issues related to the educational landscape.

Scope and Limitations

The study was conducted at Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City. The research was limited to this school, and the findings may not be generalizable to other regions and divisions. The study was conducted during the School Year 2023-2024. It examined the perceptions and appreciation of the Filipino subject during this specific academic year.

It involved Junior High School teachers in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the specified school year. The research centered on the Filipino subject as a subject of interest. It explored teachers' attitudes, perceptions, and experiences related to this subject.

The study focused on specific grade levels within high school, a specific range, but it did not include all grade levels. The study did not explore variations in language, dialects, or regional languages within Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City that students may be using, as it primarily focused on the Filipino subject.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The education landscape in the Philippines has been undergoing significant transformations in recent years, driven by technological advancements and evolving pedagogical approaches. This research used a qualitative methodology, specifically the phenomenological approach, to delve into the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how high school teachers perceived and appreciated the Filipino subject amidst these changes in the Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024. The study involved a total of fifteen (15) participants: comprised of Junior High School teachers from Koronadal National Comprehensive High School in DepEd Koronadal City Division, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria.

This study employed a Purposive Sampling Technique were intentionally utilized to carefully select fifteen (15) participants comprised of Filipino teachers from Junior High School of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School in the Division of Koronadal City, who met the researcher's specified inclusion criteria.

This research used a semi-structured interview will function as an investigative instrument during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). Its purpose is to explore the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceive and appreciate the Filipino subject amidst these changes in the Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

Based on the results, traditional teaching methods in Filipino education were perceived as predominantly teacher-centered, focusing on lectures, readings, and

didactic instruction. While some teachers may benefit from these methods, there were also concerns about passive learning experiences and limited engagement.

Further, the modernized approaches to teaching Filipino involved integrating technology, such as laptops, tablets, and multimedia resources, to create interactive and dynamic learning experiences. Teachers generally viewed these methods as effective in enhancing engagement and comprehension compared to traditional approaches, particularly for audio-visual learners.

Furthermore, teachers' preferences for either traditional or modernized approaches to learning the Filipino subject were influenced by factors such as their learning styles, engagement levels, and the effectiveness of instructional methods. While some teachers may thrive in traditional environments, others preferred modernized approaches that cater to diverse learning needs.

Finally, results show that the use of technology and digital resources positively impacted teachers' engagement with and appreciation of the Filipino subject. Technology serves as a motivational tool, fostering active participation and providing access to interactive learning materials. However, there is also recognition of the importance of balancing traditional and modern approaches to ensure a comprehensive educational experience.

Generally, these findings collectively highlighted the complex interplay between traditional and modern teaching methods in Filipino education and underscored the importance of catering to diverse student needs and preferences.

Conclusions

Based on the provided results, here are four major conclusions:

First, Junior High School teachers generally perceived traditional teaching methods in Filipino education as teacher-centered, with a focus on lectures, readings, and didactic instruction. While some teachers may find value in traditional methods, others may struggle with passive learning environments and limited engagement.

Second, modernized approaches to teaching Filipino in Junior High Schools included the integration of technology, interactive online platforms, multimedia resources, and collaborative tools for group projects. These modern approaches aim to enhance student engagement, participation, and comprehension by catering to diverse learning styles and preferences.

Third, teachers' preferences for traditional or modernized approaches to learning the Filipino subject were influenced by factors such as teaching environment, availability of instructional materials, and personal learning styles. While some teachers may benefit

from aspects of traditional teaching, others prefer modernized approaches that offer dynamic and interactive learning experiences.

Finally, it has been concluded that the use of technology and digital resources positively impacts Junior High School teachers' engagement with and appreciation of the Filipino subject by providing interactive learning experiences and easy access to academic materials. While technology serves as a motivational tool for students, concerns exist regarding overreliance on gadgets and a potential hindrance to critical thinking skills. Also, teachers' adoption of technology enhanced their connection to the subject and fosters active participation in learning, suggesting a shift towards a more student-centered and innovative approach to Filipino education.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

1. Department of Education (DepEd) of the Division of Koronadal City may encourage professional development opportunities for Filipino teachers to enhance their digital literacy skills and proficiency in integrating technology into their teaching practices.
2. Curriculum Developers/ Education Supervisor in Filipino may collaborate with educators, researchers, and technology experts to design curriculum frameworks that incorporate modernized teaching approaches while respecting the cultural and linguistic heritage embedded in the Filipino subject.
3. Filipino Teachers may foster a student-centered learning environment by incorporating interactive activities, multimedia resources, and collaborative projects that promote active participation, critical thinking, and creativity among students.
4. Future Researchers may conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of modernized teaching approaches on student learning outcomes, academic achievement, and retention in the Filipino subject.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before initiating this research, it is imperative to emphasize the paramount importance of ethical considerations in investigating the evolving educational landscape, with a particular focus on understanding how Junior High School teachers perceived and appreciated the Filipino subject amidst these changes in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, Division of Koronadal City during the School Year 2023-2024.

To facilitate the implementation process, the aforementioned plans and suggestions were presented and formally provided to East-West Mindanao Colleges, Inc.

This step was crucial to guarantee strict compliance with mandated rules and regulations. As a result, the following ethical concepts were given prominence:

The study adhered to rigorous ethical standards to ensure the protection and well-being of participants. Informed consent was meticulously obtained from the school principal, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives, methodologies, risks, and benefits. Participation was entirely voluntary, with participants having the autonomy to withdraw at any time without consequences. To safeguard anonymity and confidentiality, pseudonyms or codes were used instead of actual names, and data were securely stored with restricted access. Sensitive topics were handled with care to minimize emotional and psychological impact, supported by a readily available support system. The researcher maintained a professional and respectful relationship with the school head, strictly avoiding any actions that could harm participants.

Additionally, strict adherence to data protection regulations was ensured, with secure storage and transmission of data. Participants were assured of their voluntary participation without coercion, and the researcher remained vigilant about potential biases, maintaining objectivity and transparency. Ethical clearance was sought from relevant institutional review boards, and the findings were reported truthfully. The research considered the potential benefits to educational practices and policies, contributing positively to the education system. Cultural sensitivity and respect for local customs were maintained, and the research design prioritized inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a wide range of perspectives. This conscientious approach ensured the study was conducted with due regard to the rights and welfare of students and teachers, offering valuable contributions to the field of education within the unique setting of DepEd in Koronadal National Comprehensive High School.

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